

Trusted Platform Module Backed Trust Anchors for Securing Internet of Things Deployments

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ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is having a significant impact on offshore monitoring since it enables the collection of data in real-time from offshore sites. Due to the interconnectedness of IoT devices and their pervasive usage, cyberattacks have far-reaching effects on a variety of different stakeholders. Particularly for secure offshore monitoring services, the repercussions of IoT security concerns can have serious consequences. To address the widespread concern and uncertainty about IoT security architecture, this study presents a conceptual framework for the adoption of a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) in the IoT, with the purpose of providing trustworthy offshore monitoring services. It provides an artifact that integrates security measures in IoT and recommends combining measured boot and remote attestation through the adoption of TPM. The TPM-based security is intended to protect users' privacy and confidentiality, guarantee protection of the services provided by an IoT ecosystem for secure offshore monitoring, and ensure the legitimacy of the data, infrastructures, and devices that make up the IoT.

KEYWORDS: Internet of Things (IoT); trusted platform module (TPM); offshore monitoring; root-of-trust; cyber security.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) plays a key role in offshore monitoring by delivering real-time data and insights that improve offshore safe operation, efficiency, and sustainability (Ghamdi & Amry, 2020). As IoT technology advances, more novel uses and enhancements in offshore monitoring and management are being feasible. The use of the IoT in offshore monitoring presents a number of obstacles, many of which are specific to the complex and distant nature of offshore settings. Addressing these issues is critical for the success of IoT implementations in offshore monitoring. To overcome these obstacles in offshore IoT monitoring, a multidisciplinary strategy comprising expertise in sensor technology, communications technology, cybersecurity, and compliance with regulations is required (Wójcicki et al., 2022).

In the context of offshore monitoring, a common layered architecture for the Internet of Things typically includes a structured framework that supports the integration of various components and technologies. Such a layered architecture as shown in Fig 1, primarily includes the business layer, application layer, data pre-processing layer, data transmission layer, and device layer known as perception and execution layer (Rayes & Salam, 2017; Xu et al., 2019). Every layer within the architecture serves a distinct purpose in the broader IoT system, offering an organized and scalable foundation for the offshore monitoring system. Because of the layered architecture, components may be updated or replaced without impacting the overall system.

Fig. 1: Common layered architecture of the Internet of Things for offshore monitoring

Due to the integration of multiple devices and the particular circumstances of offshore settings, specific security concerns develop when offshore monitoring is coupled with the adoption of Internet of Things technologies. Given are the few security challenges (Rekha et al., 2023) in the setting of IoT-enabled offshore monitoring:

Network Vulnerabilities:

Challenge: IoT devices in offshore monitoring systems interact over a variety of networks, including satellite, cellular, and, in certain settings, the internet.

Impact: Vulnerable network connections can expose data to interception, alteration, and unwanted access, jeopardizing data integrity and confidentiality.

Device Authentication and Access Control:

Challenge: It is difficult to ensure secure authentication and access control for a diverse set of IoT devices, particularly in circumstances with a blend of authorized and unauthorized users.

Impact: Inadequate authentication measures might allow attackers to alter or disrupt monitoring systems.

Data Privacy Challenges:

Challenge: Offshore monitoring systems generate and transfer sensitive data, posing privacy concerns and potential regulatory infringement.

Impact: Unauthorized access to or exploitation of sensitive data can result in legal repercussions and harm the organization's reputation.

Integration Complexity:

Challenge: Integrating multiple IoT devices and technologies in offshore monitoring systems can be difficult, resulting in possible

security breaches.

Impact: Device incompatibility or a lack of defined security standards may bring vulnerabilities into the whole system.

Remote Location and Limited Access:

Challenge: Offshore monitoring systems are increasingly placed in isolated places with little physical access, making it challenging to safeguard the equipment.

Impact: Unauthorized physical access to IoT devices and monitoring equipment can lead to tampering, theft, or sabotage.

To address the security of the internet of things demands a strategy that is both comprehensive and preventative, taking into consideration both the technological and operational factors. Intuitively, many researchers believe that software alone could never be entirely secure if it is not supported as well as integrated with hardware (Sadhu et al., 2022). Therefore, this research study provides an insight of how a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) could be used in the Internet of Things to deliver secure offshore monitoring services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A safe computing environment is critical for developing technologies such as IoT and cyber-physical systems. A diverse range of research articles have shown numerous concerns concerning security in IoT architecture including devices, communication protocol, and platform, and also distinct solutions are proposed. Connecting with the range of devices is becoming more prevalent as dependence on on-demand and ubiquitous services grows. Dynamic formation and verification/validation of digital trust are critical in such a raging and ever-changing environment. The basic distributed trust paradigm, which is based on distributed consensus procedures, brings TPM to IoT systems and changes distributed primitives within the framework of TPM-enabled APIs. In this context, a recent study (Berbecaru & Sisinni, 2022) developed a methodology for mitigating software modification attacks on operating processes, data, and file configuration on an IoT device using trusted computing approaches and remote attestation. A verifier node in the proposed architecture continually watches the attester and confirms its integrity using the TPM and remote attestation protocol. Tests revealed that remote attestation may be completed in a matter of seconds, limiting the window of vulnerability of such devices to attacks. A defensive method developed by (Huang et al., 2022) made use of several Trusted Platform Modules and a blockchain oracle. The distributed blockchain oracle was presented to achieve off-chain verification outcomes for smart contracts by leveraging various TPMs verification findings. The smart contracts might well then use the off-chain verification result to detect poisoning assaults and immutably put the unique identities of non-threatening IoT devices. The security aspects and the performance demonstrated the resilience and efficiency of the method.

A TPM extension scheme (xTSeH) is proposed by (Lu et al., 2021) for smart IoT health devices. The authors of xTSeH have extended the functionalities of a TPM deployed in a smart embedded devices (TSED) to non-TPM-protected smart embedded devices (N-TSED) through the network. A TPM in the format of a kernel module is intended to serve as the trust foundation for the N-TSED which is the TPM's representation in TSED. The three protocols are presented to achieve integrity verification and inter-SED authentication. The examination of experimental system performance data demonstrates the viability and usability of the strategy. A Multiple-Tier Remote Attestation (MTRA) protocol designed by (Tan et al., 2017), took advantage of resource and processing capacity variations across various types of networked IoT devices. Devices with a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) were validated using trusted hardware, while others used software-based attestation. MTRA proved to be the versatile

method of verifying software integrity in heterogeneous IoT devices.

A study of trust at the device level covers security vulnerabilities in generic Internet of Things architectural layers (Akeem Yekini et al., 2019). It examined three prominent vendors' IoT security solutions and found that none of the IoT solutions investigated provide security at the device level of the IoT architectural paradigm. The study recommends implementing a unique device identifier and Trusted Platform Module on IoT devices and gateways for cryptography, authentication, and device management to address concerns at the device level of the architecture. Calvo et al. presented an attestation solution based on the trusted platform module that is dedicated to delivering Remote Attestation as a Service (RAaaS) while ensuring critical qualities such as adaptability, flexibility, domain separation, and authorized activation. The suggested approach may demonstrate the dependability of edge devices and IoT devices to cloud data center services.

The concept of a cryptographic Key Generating and Renewing (KGR) system was presented by Furtak (Furtak, 2020). The solution was to employ the TPM to enable the processes of generating keys, building trust structures, safeguarding stored data, and securing data transfer across system nodes. The system's key functions were securing the distribution of new symmetric keys and the renewal of keys that had previously expired for data exchange entities. The KGR approach was specifically for clusters of IoT nodes. Another study (Ali et al., 2018) devised and developed a lightweight Linux kernel security module for IoT devices that is scalable enough to monitor many kernel programs. The newly developed approach can test and report on the static and dynamic behavior of numerous applications at the same time. programs Machine learning techniques are used to verify the behavior of programs. The outcome demonstrates that the verifier can successfully detect deviant activity. A research study conducted by Lenard et al. (Lenard et al., 2023) addressed the issue of secret protection by demonstrating how the TPM standard may act as a vault in securing sensitive data in embedded systems. Platform Configuration Register (PCR) regulations govern how secrets are stored in the TPM. Unlocking, on the other hand, is accomplished by TPM unsealing. When connecting with the TPM, secure and authenticated sessions are ensured in both circumstances. Furthermore, the study developed a straightforward TPM attestation technique for validating the system state and TPM implementation. To assess the execution timings of TPM operations, a set of experiments were performed on base hardware with two alternative TPM configurations.

Furthermore, various methods have been offered to address security issues in IoT devices, such as the trusted boot or startup of the device itself. Zhao et al. (Zhao et al., 2021) analyzed the principle and method of circuit design which verifies the preset information of the embedded device before starting the embedded device, to ensure that the start process of the embedded device is carried out in the predetermined to measure and ensure the integrity of the start process. According to the trial results, the security module provides enhanced security features and reduced latency. The schema by (Shang et al., 2020) utilizes TPM and Xilinx Zynq-7030 to provide a trusted computing environment for industrial applications and accomplish the trusted startup procedure. The experiment results suggest that this strategy can successfully avoid malicious code during the embedded system startup procedure.

It is evident from the literature review that researchers have tackled the security issue of IoT in a variety of fields. However, it received less attention when it came to procuring offshore monitoring services. Securing offshore monitoring is critical to ensuring data integrity, confidentiality, and availability, as well as overall operational safety. Offshore IoT devices are vulnerable to a variety of cyber-attacks, including data theft, privacy breaches, and tampering. Because offshore monitoring systems frequently engage with sensitive data and vital activities, they are appealing targets for malicious attackers. There is a need to address device security and improve the security condition of

offshore monitoring systems in order to assure the dependability and safety of key activities.

SECURE OFFSHORE MONITORING USING TPM

As multiple services in offshore monitoring share the physical platforms, new security paradigms and issues arise which lead to new dimensionality of secure offshore monitoring (Williams et al., 2022). The use of IoT in offshore monitoring raises questions about the confidentiality and integrity of the data that is outsourced.

The physical platform of IoT supplies the trust indications that are necessary for an organization such as a physical firewall or security software. Without the assistance of a component in the hardware that can be trusted, it is impossible to guarantee the integrity and reliability of these indicators (tamper-resistant) (Sadhu et al., 2022). Because of this, the Trusted Computing Group (TCG) has delegated the utilization of the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) (Arthur et al., 2015). An illustration of using TPM integrated devices in internet of things for secure offshore monitoring is shown in Fig 2.

Fig. 2: Internet of Things based offshore monitoring environment with TPM-integrated devices

The TCG has developed trusted computing technology to address computer security issues by enhancing hardware security. This is accomplished by using a physical chip named trusted platform module (TPM), which guards against tampering when running on systems where the chip is incorporated, further assuring that the system is operating as intended (Chakrabarti et al., 2020). By modifying the accompanying software and enhancing the underlying hardware, trusted computing refers to the technologies that leverage hardware-based roots of trust to increase computer security.

The TPM, developed by the TCG consortium, is a tamper-resistant coprocessor chip that offers the hosting platform a variety of security options, including trusted boot, remote attestation, integrity checking, and cryptographic functions. Many modern personal computers (PCs) and computing devices come pre-integrated with TPM and take advantage of its security features. Version 1.2 of the TPM specification was released in 2011, while TPM 2.0 was released in 2016 with improved support for algorithms and increased cryptographic capabilities (Arthur et al., 2015). The core components of TPM as shown in Fig. 3 consist of a cryptographic processor (includes: random number generator, Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) key generator, encryption-decryption engine, etc.), persistent memory (includes: storage root key-SRK, endorsement key-EK), and versatile memory (includes: storage keys, attestation identity keys-AK, and platform configuration registers-PCR) (Arthur et al., 2015).

TPMs feature certain memory regions known as platform configuration registers (PCR), storing crucial security information such as measured values. In addition to safe storage, the TPM keeps one unique endorsement key (EK) for cryptographic operations. This key is created during the TPM manufacturing process, and the private part of the key has never been removed from the TPM. At the time of remote attestation, attestation identity keys (AK) are employed to ensure the confidentiality of the system's identification. When an attester gets a request for a remote attestation system (from a verifier), it generates an authenticity report that includes PCR values and digital signatures created using an AK. The fact that the private component of the AK has never been removed from the TPM guarantees the report's legitimacy and authenticity.

Fig. 3: Main components of Trusted Platform Module (TPM)

TPM can be used in IoT for secured Offshore monitoring for a variety of objectives, including adding an additional layer of protection to operations, storage, communications, and monitoring. Some of the core operations are listed as follow:

1. Key generation and providing secure storage of the key: The TPM has the capability to generate cryptographic keys and save them securely within the TPM. In TPM, keys can then be produced in one of three ways: via seed, via random number generator, or importing them into the TPM.
2. Integrity measurement: The new version of TPM (version 2.0) have agility in terms of hash functions. The TPM can virtually use hash algorithm such as SHA-256, advanced encryption standard (AES) symmetric algorithm (Osborn & Challener, 2013), and elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) asymmetric algorithm (Chen & Urian, 2016). The TPM has the ability to compute and store hash values for various system components in its registers.
3. Remote attestation: The mechanism of remote attestation/distributed attestation can be provided using TPM (Wagner et al., 2020). It enables an entity to authenticate itself with another remote entity, which has a number of implications in the context of the IoT environment. In a sense, the entity demonstrates to the requester with its state that it is trustworthy and the underlying system is not compromised or tampered (Kuang et al., 2022).
4. Cryptographic operations: TPM co-processor is capable of performing cryptographic operations by providing features including generating random number, hashing, performing symmetric/asymmetric encryption, and generating keys (Arthur et al., 2015).
5. Measured boot: This feature can be provided by the TPM through the use of integrity measurement. Whenever a system begins the booting process, then the TPM evaluates and performs an integrity

measurement on the various hardware, software, and firmware components to guarantee that the system was not altered or tampered with prior to the booting process.

This research work develops an artifact that specifies the security actions applicable to the secured offshore monitoring process while utilizing the TPM. This artifact contributes to a solution to the problem of integrating security in IoT, and proposes the usage of measured boot and remote attestation using TPM, as explained in the following sections.

MEASURED BOOT

The measured boot is intended to build trust in a boot context. Several components are executed step by step throughout the boot process. At first appearance, however, each component appears to be untrustworthy since some of these components may have been swapped with a malicious component. The user would be unaware of a malicious component doing the same activity as the original, but the device may be compromised.

In the measured boot method (Belay, 2022), in which pre-boot software (firmware and OS system bootloaders) uses the TPM to ensure that no changes have occurred in the pre-boot environment. On a trustworthy platform, all software should be "measured" (that is, hashed) before execution. Measured Boot is a fundamental component of the TCG architecture and serves as the foundation for the other use cases. Starting with power-on, each piece of code performed measures the following piece of code and extends a PCR before executing it.

When implementing measured boot, the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) is frequently employed. The procedure guarantees a safe system boot and meticulously records and tracks all boot steps so that their integrity may be checked later. Measured Boot with TPM can operate as follows:

1. **Hardware Initialization:** The boot process begins, and the hardware components are initialized.
2. **TPM Initialization:** The TPM is set up at the beginning of the boot process. The TPM offers cryptography and secure storage capabilities.
3. **Root of Trust for Measurement (RTM):** The TPM sets up a trustworthy baseline for measurements called the Root of Trust for Measurement (RTM). This is often a reliable firmware or piece of code. The TPM keeps track of the RTM readings that it receives.
4. **Boot Loader Measurement:** The TPM measures the hash (a cryptographic representation of the boot loader's content) and stores it in a place within the TPM called the Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs).
5. **Operating System Kernel Measurement:** The TPM calculates the operating system kernel's hash and appends it to the PCR as soon as it is loaded.
6. **Device Drivers and System Services:** Device drivers and core system services are still being loaded while the PCR is updated with the hash of each newly added component.
7. **Application Measurement:** After the OS has finished loading, it can begin launching programs and services, measuring their hashes, and adding them to the PCR.
8. **PCR Contents:** The TPM's PCRs have been updated to include a set of measures that characterize the components' integrity when they are booted. A PCR composite or PCR digest is the outcome of all of the readings being added together.
9. **Secure Boot Verification:** Secure Boot and Measured Boot are frequently used together. With Secure Boot enabled, only verified and signed code is permitted to run at boot time.

The given steps create a chain of trust, that measures the boot process with TPM to offer a safe platform for the system. If any component of the boot process is compromised, the measured value recorded in the

PCR will change, indicating probable manipulation or compromise.

REMOTE ATTESTATION

In the context of the Internet of Things (IoT), remote attestation using a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) accomplishes verifying the integrity and security state of an IoT device. A remote attestation security technique (Fraune et al., 2023) enables a distant system to validate a device platform's integrity and security. Remote attestation uses TPM to demonstrate the trustworthiness of a system to a remote party without disclosing sensitive information. TPM remote attestation is useful in a variety of contexts, including facilitating secure communication between two entities by assuring that both sides can verify the integrity of each other's systems and, eventually, the integrity of IoT devices.

Applications in IoT for secure offshore monitoring can establish their identity through remote attestation. It is used to demonstrate that a foreign entity is trustworthy and intact. The basic form of the remote attestation protocol is given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Remote Attestation Operations

Steps	Operation	Description
Step A	Create a Key	The application "X" generates a public/private key pair PK & SK and certifies uses TPM.
Step B	Compute hash	Compute the hash value Y# using the TPM of the executable code of program "Y".
Step C	Create certificate	The TPM creates a certification including PK and Y# and signs it with the attestation identity key SK_{AIK}
Step D	Authentication	When application "X" needs to authenticate itself remotely it sends the certificate of its public key and hash value A# along with a certificate issued to the TPM by a trusted certification authority (CA).
Step E	Certificate chain	The remote party then verifies the certificate chain.
Step F	Status update	Attestation status is sent if application "A" is deemed trustworthy.

CONCLUSION

This research study proposed a conceptual framework for the use of a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) in the Internet of Things (IoT), to address the prevalent concerns and skepticism around IoT security design. With the goal of offering secure offshore monitoring services, the use of TPM in IoT is proposed by providing an artifact that specifies the usage of measured boot and remote attestation using TPM. The measured boot ensures the integrity of a computing device's boot process thus ensuring the boot sequence of the device in IoT setup have not been tampered or compromised. Using TPM for remote attestation in IoT helps to develop a more secure and trustworthy IoT ecosystem by resolving issues about data security, providing root-of-trust and overall system trustworthiness. The future work is intended to integrate and assess it in the real offshore monitoring environment.

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